

FLIGHT DYNAMICS EVALUATION FOR THE T3 SUBORBITAL FLIGHT TEST

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1. Project overview
2. Reference configuration
3. Mission feasibility analysis
4. Post-MECO flight dynamics analysis
5. Grid fins control strategy
6. Entry corridor analysis
7. Reference trajectory update
8. Conclusions and way forward

SALTO overview

- SALTO - reusable Strategic Space Launcher Technologies & Operations
- Funded by the European Union in the frame of the Horizon Europe programme
- Supports the ESA Themis programme
- T1H hop tests
- Technology maturation for T3 and future launcher configurations

26

Project
partners

12

Countries
represented

38

Months to reach
the objective

2

Flight test
demonstrations

SALTO overview

Reference configuration

T3 configuration:

- ~30m-tall large-scale model of 1st stage of a VTVL heavy launcher
- Integrates 3 Prometheus engines
- ~24 tons dry mass, ~55 tons propellant

Reference configuration

Mission feasibility analysis

ArianeNext, F9 and RETALT are expected to be relatively similar launchers in terms of payload capacity.

Geometric differences are mainly due to the choice of propellant. Therefore, the 1st stage of these launchers are expected to fly relatively similar trajectories.

Launcher	Payload to LEO	Payload to GTO
Falcon 9 ¹	22.8 t (expendable) 17.5 t (DRL)	8.3 t (expendable) 5.5 t/3.5 t (DRL/RTLS)
RETALT	20 t (DRL/RTLS)	-
Ariane Next ²	-	>7 t (expendable) >4.5 t (DRL)

¹Capabilities and Services. SpaceX. 2024

²Patureau de Mirand, A. et al (July 2019). Ariane Next, a vision for a reusable cost-efficient European rocket. 8th EUCASS. doi:10.13009/EUCASS2019-949

Mission feasibility analysis

Mission feasibility analysis

● Design option that allows having aerodynamic reentry conditions similar to F9, minimizes mass consumption, and guarantees similar R2/R3 boost time = 10s

● Design option that allows having aerodynamic reentry conditions similar to RETALT, minimizes mass consumption, and guarantees similar R2/R3 boost time = 8s

Post-MECO flight dynamics analysis

- After 11s of simulation, the α reaches 40° and aerodynamic data is being extrapolated.
- Even before the extrapolation area is reached, vehicle's attitude is diverging with nominal pitch-rates of $10\text{-}20^\circ/\text{s}$. Roll and yaw rates are $< 1^\circ/\text{s}$.
- After 30s, the yaw rate also increases above $10^\circ/\text{s}$.

Grid fins control strategy

X-wing configuration

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_1 &= \delta_a - \delta_e - \delta_r \\ \delta_2 &= \delta_a - \delta_e + \delta_r \\ \delta_3 &= \delta_a + \delta_e + \delta_r \\ \delta_4 &= \delta_a + \delta_e - \delta_r \end{aligned}$$

- Rotation of any grid fin produces aerodynamic moments on all three axes.
- Higher control authority.
- Higher use/weight on the grid fin actuators.
- Coupled control channels.

Plus-wing configuration

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_1 &= \delta_a - \delta_r \\ \delta_2 &= \delta_a - \delta_e \\ \delta_3 &= \delta_a + \delta_r \\ \delta_4 &= \delta_a + \delta_e \end{aligned}$$

- AEDB re-processed with a 45° rotation along x-axis.
- Lower control authority (saturation occurs earlier).
- Lower use/weight on the grid fin actuators.
- Decoupled control channels.

Grid fins control strategy

X-wing configuration

$$\begin{aligned}\delta_1 &= \delta_a - \delta_e - \delta_r \\ \delta_2 &= \delta_a - \delta_e + \delta_r \\ \delta_3 &= \delta_a + \delta_e + \delta_r \\ \delta_4 &= \delta_a + \delta_e - \delta_r\end{aligned}$$

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Entry corridor analysis

Nominal

Monte Carlo

Entry corridor analysis

Nominal

Monte Carlo

Two further assumptions are injected to improve the corridor

1. Reducing by half the aerodynamic uncertainty (12.5% instead of 25% of the value).
2. Displacing the CoG towards the MEB in order to increase the grid fins lever arm.

Entry corridor analysis

Nominal

Monte Carlo

① 50% AEDB UF

② 3m ΔCoG

Reference trajectory update

Trajectory updated needed due to **new Prometheus model**, updated **AEDB 1.1**, and **lessons learned** from previous analyses.

Two further assumptions are injected to update the reference trajectory:

1. **Assuming that no partial MECO is performed**, and trying to reproduce ArianeGroup's original reference.
2. **Assuming that partial MECO is performed**, turning off two of the three engines when the altitude reaches 20 km.

Reference trajectory update

Reference trajectory update

Conclusions and way forward

- The mission engineering activities demonstrated that the **suborbital flight test of the T3** vehicle is feasible and could also guarantee an **adequate representativity of the expected operational conditions**.
- An analysis methodology was introduced to **define and evaluate performance maps for the flight test** and support the identification on promising design points.
- The **baseline mission** identified was **consolidated** and verified in full alignment **with the most detailed vehicles models** made available during the activity.
- The assessment of the capabilities of the proposed configuration is **supporting the consolidation of the aerodynamic characterisation of the T3 vehicle**, currently ongoing in the framework of SALTO.
- Moreover, the **flight dynamics evaluation is supporting also the consolidation of control laws**¹ that will be evaluated considering also uncertainties and dispersions:
 - Testing will be performed with Model-in-the-Loop (MIL), Software-in-the-Loop (SIL), and Processor-in-the-Loop (PIL) approaches with the goal of reaching $TRL \leq 5$ at the end of the activity.

¹Guadagnini J., De Zaiacomo G., et al., **End-to-end GCN Solution for Reusable Launch Vehicles**, MDPI Aerospace Journal special issue on Modelling, Simulation and Control of Launch Vehicles, 2025.

Thank you!

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